

Six All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project upland trials from 1982 to 1984 at Faizabad compared IET7613 with N22. Soil was a sandy loam with 57% sand, 27% silt, and 14% clay. Field capacity and permanent wilting coefficient of the 0-15 cm soil profile were 22.5 and 4.6% with bulk density 1.42 g/cm³. After rains had softened the soil, it was tilled and 100 kg seed/ha was drilled 4-5 cm deep in open furrows at 20-cm spacing and covered with soil. Fields were sown the 1st wk of July, except for 1 yr, when sowing was in the 1st wk of August. The crop received 60-13-25 kg NPK/ha and a foliar spray of Zn sulfate 2 wk after germination. Weeding was by hand.

Average rainfall for the 3 seasons was 1268 mm but distribution was erratic (see figure). In 1982, a 10-d dry spell occurred at seedling stage and rains almost stopped after 14 Sep. In 1983, there were 15-d dry spells in mid-July and August and rain stopped on 13 Oct. In 1984, rainfall exceeded 400 mm the 2d wk, there were dry periods in August, and rains stopped in mid-September.

IET7613 performed better than N22 because it has greater sink potential, higher nutrient use efficiency, and better drought resistance (see table). *ℓ*

Characters of improved IET7613 and traditional N22 grown at Faizabad, India.

Character	N22	IET7613 ^a
Agronomic		
Duration (d)	85	85 n.s.
Height (cm)	104	86***
Leaf	Large groopy	Small erect
Maturity synchrony		
Between panicles	Synchronous	Synchronous
Within panicles	Acropetal uniform	Acropetal uniform
Grain type	Short bold	Long bold
Yield		
Panicles (no./m ²)	315	410 n.s.
Grain (no./panicle)	69	62***
1000-grain weight (g)	20	27***
Ripening (%)	78	81 n.s.
Yield (t/ha)	3.3	3.8***
Physiological		
Sink potential (g/panicle)	1.24	1.90***
Nutrient use efficiency (kg grain/kg N)	52	61***
Harvest index (%)	47	49 n.s.
Productivity (kg grain/d per ha)	39	45***
Spikelet sterility (%)	22	19 n.s.
Seed dormancy (fresh harvest)	Present	Absent
Lodging	Susceptible	Resistant
Root growth	Abundant thick	Abundant thick
Root penetration	Strongly geotropic	Moderately geotropic
Drought response		
Leaf water potential (-bar)	19	21***
Relative water content (%)	66	64***
Leaf rolling (score)	5 (complete rolling)	3 (partial rolling)**
Drought sustenance (d)	9.1	10.4**
Panicle exertion	Well exerted	Moderately well exerted**
Stem extension growth	Very slow	Almost ceases
Drought injury	2	3 n.s.
Post-drought recovery score	2 (slow)	1 (fast) n.s.

^a***significant at P = 0.001, ** significant at P = 0.01, n.s. (not significant).

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

ADVERSE SOILS TOLERANCE

Varietal evaluation of rice genotypes in coastal saline soil

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The IRSATON screening set (61 entries) from IRTP was evaluated for salinity tolerance and grain yield along with local checks CSRI, CSR3, and CSR6. The seeds of 64 genotypes were sown on 13 Jul and transplanted on 17 Aug 1983 in randomized block design with 3 replications. Each entry was transplanted in 3 rows of 20 hills each; row and plant spacing was 25 cm. N at 70 kg/ha was in 2 splits. In situ soil

salinity ranged from 7.5 to 8.4 dS/m at transplanting and 5.8 to 10.1 dS/m at flowering. Data on agronomic attributes were collected from five plants selected at random in each replication, and survival rate at maturity was determined. Data on quantitative characters of 25 genotypes whose tolerance scores at the vegetative stage, at maturity, or at both stages ranged from moderate (4 to 5) to excellent (3) are given in the table.

CSR1, CSR3, and CSR6 were scored highly tolerant at vegetative and maturity stages. CSR1 grain yield was highest (1.4 kg/plot), followed closely by that of CSR3 (1.3 kg/plot) and CSR6 (1.28 kg/plot). Spikelet sterility, which is

highly affected by soil salinity, averaged 22%; the maximum was 31% in CSR6 and the lowest was 14% in CSR3. Plant survival at maturity was 98%. Other genotypes rated highly tolerant with similar spikelet sterility and plant survival were, in order of merit, C14-1, IR4630-22-2-5-1-3, and IR4422-6-2. Their lower yield may be due to their lower yield potential.

IR4630-22-2-17 had a salinity tolerance score of 3 at the vegetative stage, but was scored 4 at maturity. Its spikelet sterility of 18% was the second lowest of the entries. With 97% plant survival and low spikelet sterility, IR4630-22-2-17 appeared highly promising.

Performance of rice genotypes in coastal saline soil, India.

Designation	Plant ht (cm)	Panicles/hill (no.)	Panicle length (cm)	Filled spikelets/panicle (no.)	Spikelet sterility (%)	Days to heading (no.)	Plant survival at maturity (%)	Salinity tolerance score		Grain yield (kg/plot)
								Vegetative	Maturity	
CSR4	71	19	15.8	78	27	81	91	4	3	0.7
C100	65	16	16.8	80	41	102	81	4	4	0.9
C14-1	78	12	20.1	90	25	102	95	3	3	1.0
IR10198-66-2	85	16	22.7	85	12	105	85	4	4	0.8
IR2053-436-1-2	91	14	18.1	93	29	107	80	5	4	0.7
IR36	64	18	17.3	71	32	106	76	5	4	0.4
IR4227-109-1-2-3	81	14	19.1	71	29	104	89	4	4	0.7
IR4422-6-2	83	12	21.0	81	35	114	95	3	3	0.7
PNL 5-30	71	16	18.0	68	44	111	81	4	5	0.7
IR4432-28-5	79	19	20.2	68	47	111	84	5	5	0.8
IR4595-4-1-13	75	9	18.5	64	39	115	99	4	4	0.4
IR4630-22-2-17	83	11	19.9	70	18	113	97	3	4	0.8
IR4630-22-2-5-1-3	85	11	19.0	68	28	108	94	4	3	0.8
IR50	66	19	15.6	67	25	96	73	7	7	0.6
IR8241-B-B650-2	127	14	20.6	64	31	103	92	4	5	0.6
IR8608-189-2-2-1-3	68	16	19.0	55	23	93	85	4	4	0.5
IR8608-298-3-1-1-2	72	19	19.0	67	24	89	89	4	4	0.8
IR9575 Sel	90	11	21.1	104	27	113	87	5	4	0.8
IR9732-119-3	75	19	19.1	99	33	102	79	5	5	0.9
Pokkali (resistant check)	119	17	20.1	70	17	104	83	6	4	0.5
IR9884-54-3	78	13	19.8	84	30	134	88	4	4	0.3
PNL-11-2	71	19	18.0	78	31	111	88	4	4	0.5
CSR1 (local check)	99	18	17.8	69	21	96	99	3	3	1.4
CSR3 (local check)	101	15	18.2	88	14	98	96	3	3	1.3
CSR6 (local check)	118	14	21.0	77	31	110	99	3	3	1.2

^a Standard Evaluation System for Rice, IRRI, 1980.

CSR4, IR36, IR4595-4-1-13, IR9884-54-3, and PNL-11-2 were scored 4 at maturity. Spikelet sterility of these genotypes ranged from 27 to 39% and survival rate from 76 to 99%. CSR4 gave the highest yield. Other entries whose tolerance scores remained almost the same at both stages but whose

survival was more than 80% are also considered tolerant at maturity.

Some entries were scored 4 or 5 (tolerant) at the vegetative stage. Although they had survival rates greater than 75%, their tolerance at maturity decreased. Spikelet sterility in these entries was as high as those of entries

such as PNL5-30 and IR4432-28-5.

Tolerance scores at vegetative stage and at maturity highly but negatively correlated ($r = -0.58^{**}$) with plot yield, as did spikelet sterility ($r = -0.48^{**}$). Only plant survival at maturity was highly and positively correlated with yield ($r = 0.60^{**}$). $\mathcal{J}$

Chemical tests for screening rice genotypes tolerant of Zn deficiency under calcareous Fluvents

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In Fluvent soils in North Bihar, India, Zn deficiency is largely caused by calcareous conditions. More than 75% of soils have low Zn. We evaluated 19 semidwarf indica rices for tolerance for Zn deficiency in calcareous Fluvents and

evaluated chemical tests for screening Zn-efficient genotypes at the Sugarcane Research Institute Farm, RAU, Pusa, in 1982.

Soil was a calcareous sandy loam with pH 8.5, EC 0.48 dS/m, 0.45% organic C, 37.5% free CaCO₃, DTPA Zn 0.35 mg/kg, and DTPA Fe 9.10 mg/kg soil. Twenty-five-day-old seedlings were transplanted in 14.4-m² plots in a randomized block design with 3 replications. NPK was applied basally at 60-22-33 mg/kg soil as urea, triple superphosphate, and muriate of potash.

Tolerance for Zn deficiency was visually scored by the 1976 *Standard evaluation system for rice*. For chemical analysis, 25 plants were taken from each plot 30 d after transplanting. Samples

were washed in acidified detergent solution and rinsed with deionized water. Shoots were dried in a forced-air circulation oven at 65° C and dry matter yield was recorded. The 3d and 4th leaves from the top of plants were separated and pulverized in a Waring blender and digested in HNO₃: HClO₄: H₂SO₄. Zn and Fe were determined in the clear aliquot with an atomic absorption spectrophotometer and P was determined colorimetrically.

In most varieties, visual symptoms of Zn deficiency developed 10-15 d after transplanting. Symptoms appeared first on the 3d and 4th leaves and gradually extended to lower leaves. Light yellow spots at the base of leaves were early symptoms. They later coalesced to give